

Visual Semiosis in Film Credits: Analysing Afrofuturist Design Elements in *Black Panther*

***Lilia Carpio-Jiménez**

Department of Communication Sciences,
Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja, Ecuador
*Corresponding author email: lcarpio@utpl.edu.ec
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3337-1647>

María Rosa Tapia Salcedo

Department of Communication Sciences,
Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja, Ecuador
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2064-2065>

Abel Suing

Department of Communication Sciences,
Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja, Ecuador
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4234-5926>

Abstract

Background: Film credits serve as more than mere informational lists; they function as narrative and symbolic devices that encapsulate the creative vision of an audiovisual production. Despite their importance, the semiotic role of credit sequences in constructing cinematic meaning remains under-researched.

Objective: This study aims to analyse the specific visual resources and semiotic strategies employed in the end-credit sequence of the film *Black Panther*.

Methodology: Adopting a descriptive qualitative approach, the research examines core elements of visual design—specifically colour, typography, and geometric shapes—within the *Black Panther* credits. This case study was selected for its significant cultural relevance within the Marvel Cinematic Universe.

Results: The findings indicate that the credits utilise a sophisticated visual aesthetic that reinforces the film's narrative symbolism. This aesthetic is articulated through an Afrofuturist perspective, deeply rooted in African cultural motifs and technological speculation.

Unique Contribution: This study advances the field of visual studies by focusing on film credits—a frequently overlooked component of cinema—and demonstrates their capacity to construct complex narrative and symbolic meanings independent of the main feature.

Conclusion: Visual design plays a fundamental role in the construction of audiovisual meaning, in which typography, colour, and geometric forms serve as essential vehicles for identity and cultural symbolism.

Key Recommendation: Future scholarship should continue to explore the intersection of Afrofuturism and sacred geometry in visual communication, as these areas remain fertile yet underdeveloped fields of study.

Keywords: credits, visual design, visual elements, Afrofuturism, sacred geometry.

Introduction

Visual elements have been present in the audiovisual industry since its inception, especially in posters and credits, though they initially played a secondary role. In *Black Panther*, the credits serve as a visual communication resource that integrates typography, colour, and geometry to create an aesthetic and cultural atmosphere. The geometric shapes refer to modernity and technology, as well as sacred geometry through symbolic patterns associated with the African worldview and Afrofuturism, contributing a contemporary aesthetic and cultural analysis to academic literature.

Studies on visual design and cinema are scarce and not recent; one that can be mentioned is Pektas Turgut (2012), who studies typography in film title sequences; however, this is a brief theoretical overview. Other studies, such as that by Kovsh and Dziuba (2022), focus on colour and its influence on a film's narrative.

Although film credits are relevant, their academic study is limited, especially in relation to cultural identity and narrative. This study proposes a qualitative-descriptive analysis of the credits for *Black Panther* (Coogler, 2018) to examine how colour, typography and geometric shapes convey meaning, reinforce the narrative and consolidate cultural identity as a visual communication strategy.

Theoretical Foundation

Sacred geometry and the African worldview

Geometry studies space, its forms and the relationship between them. In ancient Egypt, “the practice of geometry was an approximation of the way in which the universe is ordered and sustained” (Lawlor, 1996, p.7).

Sacred geometry can be defined as laws or rules that structure all existence, that is, the set of proportions and patterns found in nature. For example, it can be associated with the golden point, the golden ratio, or the divine proportion, as proposed by Luca Pacioli. This rule can be seen in countless objects in nature: plants, animals, and different forms of life, as well as in weather patterns, the rotation of the planets, cosmic alignments, and even in DNA. Furthermore, ancient civilisations, architects, philosophers, and artists applied the

fundamentals of sacred geometry in the design of cities, temples, and cathedrals, as well as in calligraphy, ceramics, paintings, and murals (Sarkisian, 2021).

Sacred geometry understands that geometric shapes and structures reflect a pre-existing order and possess symbolic and spiritual meaning. From this perspective, the physical world is conceived as a manifestation of the sacred, where geometry allows us to understand and give meaning to the relationship between the visible and the symbolic.

Sacred geometry seeks to explore and understand the shapes and patterns found in the universe and relate them to symbolic and spiritual aspects. This relationship is evident in the vestiges and practices of various ancient cultures, including African, European, and American tribes, among others. There are several figures in geometry; however, “the five Platonic solids consisting of the tetrahedron, cube, octahedron, dodecahedron, and icosahedron are the sacred geometric shapes that form the basis of all matter” (Sarkisian, 2021, p.6).

Other basic shapes include the circle, which is associated with the sun, the sky, perfection, and even eternity. It can be related to unity and divinity, as the sun has been worshipped in many ancient cultures. The triangle can be an emblem of the trinity; it also represents fire and the upward impulse of everything towards higher unity (Cirlot, 1992). It is also associated with concepts of stability, balance and permanence.

Across cultures, the repetition of similar geometric shapes or fractals can be observed in paintings, textiles, dwellings, and other contexts. African architecture, which serves as the reference point for the Black Panther narrative, is highly diverse; examples of fractal architecture can be found throughout the African continent. “African settlements often display the characteristic of 'self-similarity', i.e. circles of circular dwellings, rectangular walls enclosing increasingly smaller rectangles, and streets where wide avenues branch off into small paths with striking geometric repetition” (Eglash, 1998, p. 21).

Examples of fractal architecture can be seen in Logone-Birni (Cameroon), where the Kotoko people built rectangular buildings contained within other rectangles. Another example can be found in the village of Ba-ila (Zambia), whose architecture is organised in concentric rings seen from above; the houses form circles that are grouped into larger circles, until they form the village. In both cases, the same structure is repeated throughout the settlement (Eglash, 1999).

In Nankani (Burkina Faso), the architecture is based on self-similarity and triangles present in the murals, which represent the zalanga: a stack of nested gourds used as domestic bowls. When stacked and tied together, they form triangles that symbolise life and death; when a person dies, the vessel breaks, and the soul is released. Geometric figures have been recurrent in African architecture and art since ancient times, as evidenced in the rock art of southern Africa, where figurative, geometric and abstract representations coexist, especially in the regions of Kafue and northern Zambezi. In Katanga, Angola, and Northern Rhodesia, geometric art used isolated and concentric circles, curved, angular, and parallel lines, and some other linear representations (León, 2012).

On the other hand, Afrofuturism is an artistic movement that addresses race, identity, justice, and freedom in Afro-descendant cultures by reimagining their history. It articulates

imagination, technology, the future, and liberation, and functions as an aesthetic and critical framework that integrates science fiction, speculative fiction, Afrocentrism, magical realism, and non-Western beliefs to reinterpret the past and project the future with a critical eye (Womack, 2013).

Afro-descendant cultures have historically faced racial discrimination and a constant struggle for the recognition of their rights. Thus, the concept of Afrofuturism seeks to “think about possible futures or ancestral futures [...], in which African and Afro-diasporic perspectives emerge that imagine (im)possible futures” (De Quadros, 2024, p.25). In other words, this concept refers to “narratives of empowerment, transformative technocultural change, audacity and aspiration of people of colour” (Sunday & Akung, 2022, p.4).

Afrofuturism is not a new movement; it emerged in the 1950s with the music of various African American jazz artists. However, the term was first formally used in the early 1990s in the document *Flame Wars: The Discourse of Cyberculture* by critic Mark Dery to refer to fiction that addresses African American issues and concerns in the context of 20th-century technoculture (Dery, 1994). Afrofuturism is a diverse artistic practice that manifests in disciplines such as painting, music, and cinema, although in cinema, there remains limited representation of racialised characters.

Some more recent examples in which the main characters are black are: *12 Years a Slave* (McQueen, 2013); *The Butler* (Daniels, 2013); *The Help* (Taylor, 2011). However, these films focus on racial issues and slavery, raising awareness and portraying the struggle for equality and human rights. Other films that seek to position characters of colour as, for example, superheroes or leaders, include *Hidden Figures* (Melfi, 2017); *Spider-Man: Into the Spider-Verse* (Persichetti et al., 2018); and the film that could be considered closer to the concept of Afrofuturism, which is the focus of this research, *Black Panther* (Coogler, 2018). This last film coincides with the concept of Afrofuturism itself, which seeks to imagine different worlds and realities through culture and technology.

Methods

The research uses a qualitative approach, characterised by the analysis of words, texts, speeches, drawings, graphics, and images to identify meanings and understand what characterises a phenomenon. The research is conducted through a descriptive study, the method of choice when direct descriptions of phenomena are desired. This type of study is especially useful for researchers who want to know the who, what, and where of events (Sandelowski, 2000).

The case study analyses the film *Black Panther* (Coogler, 2018), produced by Marvel Studios in collaboration with Fox Searchlight Pictures and distributed by Walt Disney Studios. This film was chosen for its widespread acceptance among the industry and the public; it has won three Oscars and received several other awards and nominations.

The study sample is limited to the film's complete credits sequence. Using video editing software, 3,997 frames were identified in a total duration of 2 minutes and 45 seconds. For the analysis, 25 main frames were intentionally selected based on the researcher's criteria. The selection was based on two criteria: a) greater representativeness, as they correspond to key

moments in the appearance of names, colours, fonts and geometric shapes, and b) narrative and aesthetic relevance.

Two main categories were established for the analysis: 1. Technical data that provide context for the story (title, year, genre, duration, and plot). 2. Visual elements that initially allow for a denotative identification of the credits sequence, for example: images (photographs, illustrations, comics, etc.); colour (warm, cool); typography (fonts); and geometric shapes (circles, triangles, fractals, etc.). Subsequently, these elements establish meanings through connotative analysis.

The methodological process includes four stages: 1) repeated viewing of the sequence to identify representative frames; 2) capture of the frames; 3) organisation of the captures grouped by characters; and 4) visual description of the elements (colour, typography and geometric shapes) with denotative and connotative analysis, considering their relationship with African culture and sacred geometry.

Results

Black Panther (Coogler, 2018) focuses on the identity of the fictional African nation of Wakanda, T'Challa's ascension to the throne, and the shift in political vision. The film, which belongs to the action, adventure, and science fiction genres, stands out for its narrative and visual approach. The credits sequence, which lasts 2 minutes and 45 seconds, is particularly relevant to this study.

Narratively, T'Challa returns to Wakanda to assume leadership and become Black Panther, facing various antagonists with the support of key allies. The story unfolds in a futuristic setting that integrates traditional elements of African culture. The visual aesthetic is central to the narrative construction: Wakanda is presented as a futuristic, technologically advanced space, enriched with African symbols and iconography, creating a synthesis of technology, tradition, and cultural symbolism.

Visual design is key to the identity of *Black Panther* and Wakanda, where typography, colour, and geometric patterns build a coherent and recognisable identity. These elements serve both aesthetic and communicative functions. From the perspective of visual communication analysis, the credits are examined based on categories such as image type, colour, typography, and geometric shapes.

Table 1. Analysis sheet for the credits sequence of the film *Black Panther*

Technical data	Denotative analysis (visual elements)	Connotative analysis (visual elements)
<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Title▪ Year of release▪ Country/Production company (publisher)▪ Director▪ Film genre▪ Running time	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Type of images▪ Predominant colour palettes▪ Typography▪ Geometric shapes	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Connotations of colour▪ Connotations of typography▪ Connotations of geometric shapes

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Running time of credits sequence ▪ General plot summary 		
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Source: Own elaboration

The Black Panther credits sequence consists of 3,997 frames, of which 25 main images feature the production team and cast. The design is based on dark-toned illustrations and silhouettes, with textures that fit the narrative, contrasted with colourful backgrounds that add dynamism and energy. This fantastical visual atmosphere captures the viewer's interest and immerses them in the world of Wakanda.

Colour in narrative

Colour is the most recognisable element in the Black Panther credits and plays a central role in the film, the costumes and the representation of Wakanda. Its use not only adds aesthetic value, but also reinforces the narrative, visual identity and status of the characters, generating symbolism that strengthens the audiovisual discourse. The sequence identifies various colour palettes associated with characters, tribes and symbolic elements. The colours present in the credits sequence are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Colours assigned to characters and elements in the narrative and in the credits

Source: Own elaboration

Purple: According to colour psychology, purple represents wisdom, vision, and truth. It is also associated with royalty, so it makes sense that it is used in the introductory sequences of two characters who belong to the royal family of Wakanda (T'Challa and Ramonda). In addition, this colour is seen in the opening sequence where two panthers are introduced, and at the end of the credits, it accompanies the film's title along with the main character transformed into Black Panther. The colour purple evokes the courage and spiritual strength of royalty.

Neon blue: It is associated with tranquillity and nature; it is used as the representative colour of vibranium, a malleable metal and the main source of wealth in the nation of Wakanda. However, this colour is also associated with technology, which is why it also represents a technological city. In the Marvel Cinematic Universe, this metal has been used to create Captain America's shield, Ultron's body, and Black Panther's suit.

Greenish blue: Although it is a colour with positive connotations, according to colour psychology, associated with nature and calm, it is also used to demonstrate egocentricity. The colour represents the so-called “outsiders”, characters who do not belong to any tribe or are the villains of the story. For example, it is used in the individual sequences of Everett Ross, T'Challa's friend, who is not from Wakanda; and for W'Kabi, who was the king's best friend, but due to a clash of ideals ends up allying himself with his enemy to seize the throne; and it is

also used for N'Jobu, who sought to attack Wakanda to steal vibranium. Therefore, this colour has a negative connotation.

In addition, this colour is used in the background of a sequence showing a group of black panthers stalking something or someone, reflecting the danger posed by outsiders to a region that has long kept its wealth secret, such as Wakanda.

Green: associated with nature and life. It is used in the individual credits for Nakia and the River Tribe, whose traditional colour is green. This tribe uses this colour in their clothing with textures based on shells and rivers in the fabrics; they wear crocodile skins and are influenced by the Suri and Mursi tribes of Ethiopia, as men in both Wakanda and the cultures wear lip plates. In the narrative, the River Tribe has closer contact with nature and is responsible for supplying provisions and food for their territory, highlighting the richness of the land and its natural resources.

Gold: In African culture, this colour is associated with wealth, power and luxury. It represents the Golden City, the capital of Wakanda, where most of the African nation's wealth is located. The gold sequences also feature figures of the Black Panther, African patterns representing the culture, the city skyline and the king's throne as a symbol of power.

Red: Associated with strength and honour, the colour red represents vitality and power in African culture. Due to its high visibility and symbolic significance, it is assigned to the Dora Milaje, King T'Challa's personal guard. Their name, which in Wakandan means "The Adored Ones" refers to a group comprising members of the 18 tribes of Wakanda, recognisable by their red costumes, shaved heads, and tattoos that identify their tribal origins. The aesthetics of the Dora Milaje are inspired by the clothing of the Maasai tribe, known for their red tunics and warrior tradition, reinforcing their symbolic role within the narrative.

The colour red visually reinforces the strength of this group of women and their importance within Wakandan society. Even in other Marvel productions, such as *Falcon and the Winter Soldier* (Skogland, 2021) and *Avengers: Infinity War* (Russo & Russo, 2018), the respect they inspire in other characters is evident. Although the Dora Milaje do not possess supernatural powers, their on-screen representation stands out for occupying a role traditionally assigned to male figures.

Orange: It is an exotic and striking colour that plays a secondary role in our thinking and symbolism. It is the colour of the frivolous or the original (Heller, 2012). Based on these meanings, its use is related to representing the main antagonist, the villain of the story, Erik Killmonger, who arrives in Wakanda seeking to avenge his father's death and seize the throne; in addition, the colour orange is close to gold, which is used to represent the Golden City.

Colour plays a central role in the narrative, as different palettes are associated with specific characters and elements: purple with royalty, red with warriors, and blue with technology. However, their meaning is enhanced when integrated with the geometric shapes in the credits sequence. Thus, the red patterns in the silhouettes of the Dora Milaje reinforce power; the yellow patterns in the city allude to a prosperous territory; and the blue, combined with purple in triangular shapes, is linked to the mineral that gives rise to their power. In this way, colour

articulates the visual discourse and strengthens the narrative of cultural identity and Afrofuturism.

Typography and symbolism

In terms of typographic analysis, and according to the production study carried out by Perception (2025), the main objective in designing the film's typography was to represent Wakandan culture using a font that simulated Wakandan glyphs (Figure 2). The final version of the typography in the individual character sequences, as well as in text plates within the film, was based on the Beyno font.

Figure 2: Wakandan Glyphs

Source: Adapted from the credits of *Black Panther*, (Coogler, 2018).

During the animation of the different sequences of the credits, and in the appearance of the texts, glyphs or characters from the Wakandan writing system are used, which have defined geometric shapes. These are transformed into comprehensible texts, i.e. Latin characters. A web search identifies the *Wakanda Forever* typeface, which simulates the glyphs (Figure 2).

In addition, slight variations in the Latin types are recognised. For example, the typeface has been modified only in the letters A, H and E, which are used exclusively for the name of the film *Black Panthers*. Even the letter A in the word “Black” receives a single modification, but the A in *Panthers* remains unchanged (Figure 3). The rest of the texts maintain the *Beyno* typeface, without modification.

These modifications are neither random nor aesthetic; the letter A is left open, and a dot is included in the centre, suggesting the king's ascension. It also suggests a spiritual connection with his ancestors, specifically with his late father. In the case of the letter H, the removal of one of its bars suggests stability. And in the letter E, removing one arm suggests rupture and dynamism. This reinforces the identity of a technological nation, but one rooted in strong ancestral traditions. Thus, the typography fulfils an informative function and becomes a symbol that unites modernity and tradition.

Figure 3: Font used for the credits

Source: Own elaboration

The Beyno typeface belongs to the geometric sans serif family and is characterised by its geometric shapes, visible in curved letters such as O, D, Q and G, and in triangular letters such as A, V and W. The texts are arranged symmetrically at different points on the screen, mainly in black, depending on the actor presented, while the film title appears centred, in white, in the same typeface. The use of the Beyno font and its modifications responds to an Afrofuturist aesthetic, simulating Wakandan writing linked to tradition and adapting it to a legible typeface associated with technology and the projection of the future.

Visual geometry

The title sequences feature illustrated silhouettes of the characters and objects that form part of the story, but there are also characteristic forms that contribute to the narrative concept, namely geometric figures (Figure 4) widely used in fractals and patterns in African culture.

Figure 4: Geometric shapes

Source: Adapted from the credits of Black Panther, (Coogler, 2018).

Elements such as points and lines are the smallest building blocks in visual design; points are the starting point for any visual form, lines establish direction, and both construct contours. These basic elements are the toolbox for all visual communication (Dondis, 2017).

The credits use basic geometric shapes: dots, lines, diamonds, triangles and circles, organised into patterns that structure the visual composition and capture the viewer's attention. These patterns, linked to African culture, have historically been used in textiles, painting, sculpture, and architecture to encode social, cultural, and spiritual meanings, thereby establishing continuity with ancestral traditions.

Associating specific meanings from African culture with each geometric figure is complex, as literature on the subject is scarce. However, the use of these shapes is not far removed from certain concepts related to the practices and rituals of different cultures, or to the concept of sacred geometry.

For example, it is evident in the sequences that the silhouettes of a golden city rise, and that fractals of vertical lines and triangular figures are placed on the walls of the buildings (Figure 4 b). This can be related to the traditional architecture of the Nankani (Burkina Faso), This African ethnic group places murals of triangles on walls, representing people and associated with a sacred concept of life and death. In the case of Wakanda, the narrative begins with King T'Challa's death and revolves around mourning, grief, and the nation's struggle to move forward and overcome threats.

Another geometric shape in fractal form is the rhombus (Figure 4a), which can be seen throughout the silhouette representing the Dora Milaje. The uniform rhombus shapes on the red background represent the power and courage of these warriors; these characters are influenced by the Masai tribe. The rhombus shape may symbolise the tips of arrows, which are these warriors' weapons of combat. Their clothing features a rhombus at the lower front of their skirts, at belly height, which is directly related to the meaning of femininity (Hentze, 1932).

One of the figures is the circle surrounded by hexagonal fractals (Figure 4e); this can be related primarily to the architecture of the Ba-ila culture of Zambia, where dwellings are arranged in concentric rings, with the main ring being the dwelling of the tribal leader. In sacred geometry, the circle is a symbol of divinity and the sky; Pythagoras represented divinity and the unity of the universe through this figure (Wright, 2018).

In addition, the hexagon stands out as a regular polygon formed by two inverted equilateral triangles within a circle (Béziau, 2012). It is one of the most common shapes in nature, found in structures such as beehives, turtle shells, snowflakes, dragonfly eyes, the scales of some fish, and fruits such as pineapples.

The hexagon represents harmony and connection with opposites; it is related to the circle, where alternating vertices can be connected with straight lines to form the hexagram, a figure composed of triangles that symbolises the “fusion of the opposing principles of masculine and feminine, heat and cold, water and fire, earth and air, etc., and is therefore a symbol of archetypal wholeness, the divine power of creation” (Pennick, 1982, p. 20). In Wakanda, it relates to royalty, leadership, and King T'Challa's relationship with the tribes.

In the credits, patterns of shapes and colours generate movement and visual harmony, evoking notions of origin, community, unity and the life cycle. These elements evoke identity and tradition while projecting technological evolution, reinforcing a fictional narrative that positions Afro-descendant cultures in a context of leadership and empowerment.

Discussion

The study shows that colour, typography and graphic forms interact to construct meaning. Colour stands out as a central resource due to its ability to evoke feelings, convey messages and generate identity (Heller, 2012), although its expressive power depends on its articulation with typography and geometric shapes. Together, these elements form a coherent visual system that communicates identity, culture and technology; thus, colour contributes to the construction of characters and narrative, helping to create atmosphere, convey symbolic meaning, and influence the viewer's perception (Kovsh & Dziuba, 2022), while its integration with geometry reinforces ideas of innovation, modernity and spiritual connection. Geometry supports a spiritual view of the world through the principles of spatial order. This ties in with Lawrol's (1996) study, which suggests that geometry helps us to understand the connection between the material and spiritual worlds.

The Beyno typeface accompanies the colour and geometric shapes, evoking a script with strong customs and traditions, and the key modifications to some letters contribute to the concept of the future, innovation and technology that corresponds to the film's narrative.

Geometric shapes bring dynamism and rhythm, as well as meanings associated with ancestral cultures and sacred geometry. Each shape has a specific symbolic value: the circle is linked to divinity (Wright, 2018), the triangle to life and death (Cirlot, 1992), and the rhombus to femininity (Hentze, 1932).

In the film *Black Panther*, the elements analysed—primarily geometric shapes—draw on traditions characteristic of various African cultures, where, as demonstrated by the studies of Eglash (1998, 1999) and León (2012), such shapes are manifested in objects, architecture and clothing. These compositions not only fulfil an aesthetic function, but also reinforce identity, cultural continuity and a sacred dimension. In this sense, these elements are linked to the concept of Afrofuturism, understood by Womack (2013) as a framework which, through fiction, imagines alternative realities capable of challenging and subverting the structures of colonial domination. Thus, the visual composition of the opening credits transcends mere ornamentation and takes shape as a symbolic space where the image acts as a vehicle for memory, culture and identity.

This study is limited to a single-case analysis, so its results cannot be generalised to all film title sequences. Future research could be extended to other Marvel Cinematic Universe products or to works with an Afrofuturist approach to identify similarities or differences in the visual resources used. Furthermore, although there are studies on audiovisual design and title sequences in cinema, these are still limited, which adds value to the present work by demonstrating how visual elements operate strategically in the construction of meaningful atmospheres.

Conclusions

This study shows that visual design and its elements play a central role in constructing meaning within the audiovisual context. Typography, colour and geometric shapes not only contribute to visual aesthetics but also function as strategic resources for visual communication. Their harmonious organisation generates symbolic communication that articulates cultural roots,

ancestry, modernity and technology, reinforcing the film's narrative and the Afrofuturist concept.

Analysis of the different elements revealed their importance in creating an attractive, functional and symbolic visual product. Typography fulfils a communicative, graphic, and aesthetic function, conveying information, serving as a visual resource, being pleasing to the eye, and building identity. In the credits, the typography reinforces the narrative linked to traditional culture, while the modifications to the letters evoke modernity, technology and a connection with the sacred.

Colour is one of the central elements, with each shade responding to a synaesthetic criterion that conveys emotions and sensations in line with the characteristics of each element and character. Likewise, the use of colour establishes a visual hierarchy among the characters and their roles within the narrative.

Analysis of the geometric shapes shows that they do not merely serve an aesthetic function, but also generate an emotional, symbolic and cultural connection that complements and reinforces the audiovisual narrative. The dots, lines and triangles organised into patterns reinforce the cultural concept associated with African tradition.

It is essential to integrate the analysis of resources such as credit sequences and the film product into training in design and visual communication to understand how audiovisual aesthetics construct meaning through various elements, thereby strengthening the skills needed to create meaningful experiences.

Although based on a single case, the study opens a line of research that can be extended to other audiovisual products, strengthening an expanding academic field and projecting itself into areas such as social media, content creation, and artificial intelligence.

Declarations

AI Use Statement: During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT and DeepL for the organisation and drafting of the text and for its translation into the language requested by the journal.] After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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